

MEDICAL SCIENCES

RESULTS OF IMMUNOLOGICAL STATUS BEFORE AND AFTER ENDOSCOPIC SURGERY IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS

Khushvakova N.,

*MD Professor Head of the Department of Otorhinolaryngology No. 1
Samarkand State Medical University
Samarkand, Uzbekistan.*

Burkhanov U.,

*Assistant of the Department of Otorhinolaryngology No. 1
Samarkand State Medical University
Samarkand, Uzbekistan.*

Nurmuhammedov F.

*Assistant of the Department of Otorhinolaryngology No. 1
Samarkand State Medical University
Samarkand, Uzbekistan*

Abstract

The article presents data on the dynamics of changes in the level of cytokines in blood serum and nasal secretions in patients with chronic rhinosinusitis. 178 patients were studied. The study showed that chronic forms of rhinosinusitis develop against the background of multidirectional shifts in the concentration of anti-inflammatory cytokines in blood serum and nasal secretions. The patients were divided into 2 large groups. After the post-operative period, patients of the main group using LILT methods showed a tendency to normalize the levels of all classes of serum immunoglobulins IgA decreased by 44.3%, IgM by 61.2%, IgG by 14.0% and secretory immunoglobulin A by 18.0%. The dynamics of changes in each indicator indicated a decrease in the immune load on the body.

Keywords: rhinosinusitis, endoscopic surgery, low-intensity laser therapy, immunoglobulin, mucociliary transport.

Relevance. Rhinosinusitis is an inflammatory disease of the mucous membranes of the nose and nasal cavities, almost always caused by secretory stagnation and impaired aeration of the nasal cavities. Inflammation of the nasal cavities is one of the most common pathologies among the ENT organs. In the last decade, the incidence of rhinosinusitis has increased almost 3 times. According to epidemiological studies, 15% of the adult population and 5% of children suffer from inflammatory diseases of the nasal cavities. The incidence of chronic inflammatory diseases of the nasal cavities remains high and still does not have a declining principle. Consequently, there has been a recent increase in morbidity by 1.5–2.0% [1].

The modern ecological environment is characterized by increasing pollution of the atmosphere by motor transport, industry and chemical organizations. Over-saturation with inhalation pathogens leading to inflammation or sensitization of the organism, as well as various physical factors (ionizing radiation, electromagnetic waves, ultraviolet rays, etc.) is observed [6]. Chemicals also lead to an increase in negative effects, as they act as irritants to the barrier tissues of the respiratory system, thereby facilitating the passage of pathogens through the UNY mucous membrane into the body's internal environment. All this leads to a decrease in immunoreactivity of the population, an increase in respiratory diseases and their transition to a chronic form [2].

Disorders of the mechanical component of protection - i.e. mucociliary transport - lead to SRS. The condition of BYOBs is primarily governed by the efficient

functioning of the mucociliary apparatus. The MA of the mucous membrane is damaged by viral and bacterial infections or other exogenous effects, as a result of which microorganisms begin to multiply in sterile cavities, multiply intensively, and lead to the development of acute rhinosinusitis [4].

Local immunity is provided by: BYoB aeration and blood circulation, mucociliary clearance, mucus formation, cellular, chemical and immunological mechanisms of the body's defense against various microorganisms. It is also known that the nasal mucosa has IgA-producing cells located in the mucous areas and IgG-producing cells located in the epithelial layer [3].

In recent years, the development of laser research in medicine has become a strategic task for the treatment of various diseases in the leading countries of the world. The ability of laser beams to generate high concentrations in space over a certain frequency range over time has opened up new prospects for biotechnology. Currently, laser technology is used in all areas of medicine: the concept of laser medicine has been formed both in the field of fundamental research, as well as in clinical practice. At the same time, the development of laser medicine is evolving across three main areas: laser surgery, laser therapy, and laser diagnostics [5].

The aim of the study is to examine the immunological status of patients with chronic rhinosinusitis before and after endoscopic surgery, as well as to evaluate the results.

Materials and inspection methods. Clinical examinations covered 178 patients with proliferative form

of chronic rhinosinusitis: All patients from 2018 to 2021 were examined and treated in the inpatient department of the ENT Department of SamDTU Clinic No. 1 and the private medical center "SAOMED" in Samar-kand.

After endoscopic surgery, patients in the main group were treated with LILT on a Mustang 2000 device (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Introduction of MUSTANG 2000

In the postoperative period, the use of LILT is performed in order to enhance the immune system, improve local blood circulation and improve the quality of wound healing. For this purpose, the treatment is performed while the patient is sitting, no analgesia of the nasal mucosa is required, endonasal wavelength 0.89

μm , maximum radiation output 5 W is performed using a special nasal cavity ENT nozzle, lower and middle nasal with ENT nozzle. The tracks are inserted and held for 1.5–2 minutes. The course of treatment - 5–7 days (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Technique of conducting nasal cavity LILT.

Blood, plasma, and serum served as the object of nasal secretion testing. Blood was drawn from the elbow vein at lunch. Serum or plasma was isolated by conventional methods. To remove the wash from the nasal cavity, a dry cloth swab was placed in each common nasal passage of the patient for 10 minutes, and after it was removed from the nose, 1 ml of 0.9% sodium chloride solution was placed in a preservative solution. Thirty minutes later, the tampons were thoroughly compressed, and the obtained, washed was used for inspections. The standardization of the washes was carried out by spectrophotometric control at a wavelength of 280 nm - "dilution - concentration".

Serum, blood plasma, and nasal secretions were taken at the same time, on the day of admission or hospitalization, as well as before the end of the course of treatment and response, usually 5-7 days in the hospital. All samples were frozen in Eppendorf-type solutions and stored at -20°C until use. Determination of Ig and

its subclasses, as well as sIgA, belonging to classes A, M, G, was carried out using the solid-phase IFA method, using binary antibody reagents.

Results and discussions. Based on the data obtained, we concluded that once a day for 5-7 days, apply PILT continuously for 2-3 minutes with infrared rays with a power of 5 mW, wavelength 0.89 μm , separately for each nasal cavity. leads to a rapid restoration of the functional state of the cavity.

Evaluation of the endoscopic picture performed in the dynamics showed that statistically reliable recovery of nasal functional status and immunologically normal blood and nasal secretions was faster in the main group of patients undergoing PILT in the postoperative period, without any additional physiotherapeutic treatment, compared with the control group. Tumors of the nasal mucosa disappeared by 5.3 ± 0.4 days in the main group of patients and by 8.7 ± 0.6 days in patients in the control group ($p < 0.05$).

Table 1

Serum outcomes of control group patients before and after treatment

Criteria g/l	Ig content before treatment is g/l		The amount of Ig after treatment is g/l	
	pointer	reliability	pointer	reliability
IgA	10,02±0,3	p<0,05	10,9±0,1	p<0,05
sIgA	0,14±0,05	p<0,05	0,23±0,03	p<0,05
IgM	3,5±0,7	p<0,05	1,7±0,2	p<0,05
IgG	10,35±1,6	p<0,05	14,0±1,4	p<0,05

Note: p are statistically significant differences between conventional and proposed therapy

Table 2

Serum outcomes of the main group of patients before and after treatment

Criteria g/l	Ig content before treatment is g/l		The amount of Ig after treatment is g/l	
	pointer	reliability	pointer	reliability
IgA	11,07±0,1	p<0,05	5,3±0,3	p<0,05
sIgA	0,25±0,02	p<0,05	0,18±0,03	p<0,05
IgM	4,63±0,3	p<0,05	1,85±0,2	p<0,05
IgG	12,45±1,2	p<0,05	15,2±1,4	p<0,05

Note: p are statistically significant differences between conventional and proposed therapy

Table 3

Outcomes in nasal secretion of control group patients before and after treatment

Criteria g/l	Ig content before treatment is g/l		The amount of Ig after treatment is g/l	
	pointer	reliability	pointer	pointer
IgA	2,58±0,9	p<0,05	3,9±0,2	p<0,05
sIgA	0,10±0,05	p<0,05	0,15±0,03	p<0,05
IgM	1,49±0,6	p<0,05	1,7±0,2	p<0,05
IgG	15,34±1,7	p<0,05	17,0±1,4	p<0,05

Note: p are statistically significant differences between conventional and proposed therapy

Table 4

Outcomes in nasal secretion of the main group of patients before and after treatment

Criteria g/l	Ig content before treatment is g/l		The amount of Ig after treatment is g/l	
	pointer	reliability	pointer	pointer
IgA	3,01±0,1	p<0,05	4,5±0,3	p<0,05
sIgA	0,14±0,02	p<0,05	0,25±0,03	p<0,05
IgM	1,53±0,3	p<0,05	1,8±0,2	p<0,05
IgG	16,25±1,3	p<0,05	17,5±1,5	p<0,05

Note: p are statistically significant differences between conventional and proposed therapy

After the proposed therapy, the concentration of sIgA, IgM, IgG in the nasal secretion increases. Undoubtedly, this pattern is associated with increased local secretion of immunoglobulins.

Thus, the table shows that the use of PILT in the postoperative period in the main group of patients is based on the principle of normalization of serum immunoglobulins of all classes, including IgA by 44.3%, IgM by 61.2%, IgG by 14.0%. and secretory immunoglobulin A decreased by 18.0%. The dynamics of changes in each indicator indicates a decrease in the immune load on the body.

Conclusion. Based on this study, it can be concluded that the success of treatment of patients with proliferative form of chronic rhinosinusitis depends not only on the quality of the surgical intervention performed, but also on the accuracy of the postoperative period, aimed at restoring the nasal mucosa and its functions.

Based on the results obtained, it can be said that after the endoscopic surgery and the course of PILT, the condition of the nasal mucosa in patients and almost rapid recovery of the body's immunological parameters are observed.

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ВА ТИББИЁТ МУАММОЛАРИ PROBLEMS OF BIOLOGY AND MEDICINE ПРОБЛЕМЫ БИОЛОГИИ. – 2019. – С. 144.

SMART HEALTHCARE SYSTEM FOR CARDIOVASCULAR PATIENTS USING MACHINE LEARNING

Kondoro A.,

Department of Computer Studies, Dar es salaam Institute of Technology, Dar es salaam, Tanzania

Tongora E.F.

Department of Computer Studies, Dar es salaam Institute of Technology, Dar es salaam, Tanzania

Abstract

Cardiovascular refers to anything relating to the heart and blood vessels. The flawed current leads to multiple patients not receiving the right care depending on their current health status, leading to critical cases and even death. Apart from the main objective of developing a smart healthcare system for cardiovascular diseases, other specific objectives include modelling a machine learning algorithm for natural language processing, modelling a machine learning algorithm for health recommendation, developing a preliminary diagnosis subsystem, developing a follow-up report management subsystem, integrating geolocation subsystem, evaluating the system. The study has proposed new method, the Recommendation and Optimization-Based Decision Support System Algorithm, constructs an expert system with an explicit knowledge base. The algorithm obtains knowledge through domain experts. In response to a query, the algorithm gives a customized recommendation, using an optimization step to help the patient maximize the probability of achieving the desired outcome. In this findings, the recommended behavioural factors are the optimal solutions that maximize the desired effect's likelihood. With proper formulation, this expert system can combine multiple factors like age and body mass index to give proper self-preliminary diagnosis support at the individual level.

Keywords: Cardiovascular, Machine learning, Healthcare

I. INTRODUCTION

The first president of the United Republic of Tanzania, the late Mwalimu Julius Kambarage, once stated the country's three main enemies were poverty, illiteracy, and diseases. A country must address several challenges for a stable economy so that its people's health is on the agenda. Diseases can slow the country's economy as countries depend on human resources to manufacture several economic tasks. A disease is a pathological process, most often physical, as in throat infection or cancer of the bronchus, sometimes undetermined in origin, as in schizophrenia [1]. The disease manifests itself as a disorder and announces its presence in the form of symptoms. Disease phenomena, cases of the disease, the clinical picture, and the course of a disease can be described, objectified, and classified [2]. Diseases are often known to be medical conditions associated with specific signs and symptoms [3]. Tanzania's government has made several efforts through the Ministry in charge of health and social welfare and other organizations to improve the health sector in Tanzania. In 2019, the Ministry of Health, Community Development, Gender, the Elderly, and Children of the United Republic of Tanzania agreed to a new health policy. This policy will reduce the burden of medical costs by ensuring a shift in preventing diseases and infections [4]. The whole situation is because these costs affect citizens at a community and national level. Despite the immense efforts emphasized by Tanzania's government, the increase in cardiovascular disease cases in the country has still been a problem. Cardiovascular disease is a particular abnormal condition that negatively

affects all or part of an organism's structure or function, but does not cause any immediate external injury [5]. Furthermore, it is an abnormal heart or blood vessel condition [6]. Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is a general term for conditions affecting the heart or blood vessels. It is usually associated with a build-up of fatty deposits inside the arteries and increased blood clots. It can also be associated with damage to arteries in organs such as the brain, heart, kidneys, and eyes. Cardiovascular diseases develop into conditions that last one year or more and require ongoing medical attention or limited daily living activities or both [7].

The categories of cardiovascular diseases include coronary artery disease, or CAD, which is the most common form of heart disease; the hardening or narrowing of the arteries that lead to the heart characterizes this condition. A heart attack, or myocardial infarction, happens when the arteries leading to the heart become blocked, disrupting blood flow. Congestive heart failure occurs when stiffness in the heart prevents the organ from pumping blood adequately through the body. Heart valve disease happens when any of the four valves in the heart do not open or close properly and interrupt blood flow. Heart muscle disease, or cardiomyopathy, can lead to heart failure. It occurs when the heart muscle becomes more extensive and stiffens, preventing it from pumping blood away from the heart. Sometimes blood can pool in the lungs. Abnormal heart rhythms, or arrhythmia, cause a fluctuation in the heart-beat that happens while at rest [8].

Tanzania, like other developing countries, is experiencing a higher burden of cardiovascular diseases.